

PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF DEVELOPING THE MEDICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE DOCTORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091753>

Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of raising a solid foundation for the future medical culture and society, strengthening both material and spiritual attention to medical science.*

Keywords: *medical culture, the development of medical science, a solid foundation for the future, information technology.*

Introduction. Today, the democratic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, new institutions, educational and health care systems, state and community management updates, which are being formed based on a critical analysis of relations in society, require social activity from every citizen and every individual. This activity depends on the physical and mental health of the subject. A patient, a patient or a person with a physical defect does not always actively react to social life and problems, he knows that his opportunities are limited, that physical or mental stress will cost him. Therefore, medical culture and healthy eating are dialectically related. 25% of the 4 meals a day should be for the first breakfast, 15% for the second breakfast, 35% for lunch, and 25% for the evening meal. Violation of this order causes cardiovascular diseases, causes obesity that interferes with the normal functioning of the body. According to sources, obesity is observed in 25% of the world, and in 50-60% of the population after the age of 40. Of course, it is worrying that obesity is observed among young people who are forming medical culture. 35% of young people in the USA and more than 20% in Europe are overweight. If necessary measures are not taken, the number of obese people may double by 2025. "Everyone can prevent a number of serious diseases by following the principles of a healthy lifestyle and rational nutrition. In fact, according to the World Health Organization, human health and longevity are 19% due to medicine, 20% due to heredity, 20% due to external influences (environmental, economic, etc.), and 50% due to her lifestyle and habits (physical activity, smoking, drinking alcohol, excess body weight, etc.), including diet." It can be seen that there is a direct connection between a healthy lifestyle based on rational nutrition and prevention of diseases, avoiding excess weight. Dietetic recommendations are not only to regulate the eating process, but ultimately to achieve results that help a person live a healthy, active, healthy and socially active life. Modern dietetics has adopted Ibn Sina's motto: "He who eats a lot eats it." Today, dietetics has created many models and rules of rational nutrition, in which the main focus is on the selection of foods and the creation of the body's digestion technology. In them, a healthy lifestyle is formed through rational nutrition, and is interpreted as the result of self-control of the individual's organism, listening to its requirements, and self-healing through starvation. However, medical culture is not only health care or rational nutrition, its multifactorial reality encourages us to look at it not only through the process of health, but also through the synthesis of economic, social, physical, and mental influences.

Research Methodology. In the development of medical culture among students Islamic physical education (physical culture, sports exercises, travel and tourism) is a factor in the development of the body resistant to external influences, beautiful from the outside, and forming

internal immunity. The human body develops by eliminating certain physical exercises and physical loads, training in this process, fighting with the surrounding obstacles, such obstacles make it strong. In Plato's work "Crito", Socrates' thoughts about gymnastic exercises are given. Socrates said that as one learns to eat and drink, "it is necessary to learn to exercise one's body." He calls gymnastics "beautiful work"¹. Gymnastic exercises are not beautiful in themselves, they have a positive effect on the development of the human body, form flexibility, agility, and harmony in it, and become something beautiful. According to A. Disterweg (1790-1866), who scientifically based the training of a person through special physical exercises and developed a didactic method in this regard, introduced it into the educational system, a person is formed through the combination of mental and physical exercises. As important as mental exercise is, physical exercise is just as important. He calls these exercises "voluntary action". "Voluntary action" appears as physical activity in the first stage of human life (up to about fourteen years of age). A child wants to play freely, a boy is active, as it should be. It is necessary not to stop it even after the age of fourteen, but it should be brought to such a level by this period that it is a developed spiritual will. Physical exercises bring pleasure to the body, peace, satisfaction from overcoming obstacles, and optimism in the soul. Therefore, A. Disterweg develops a method of harmoniously conducting physical and mental exercises in education. In this method, everything, the whole life is built on certain laws, and education is built on the principles of understanding these laws and organizing them according to them, so physical exercises serve mental development.

Conclusion. According to researches, the medical culture is based on healthy living, glorifying health and striving to use all the necessary opportunities for it is common sense, an open path to health. An introvert's desires may sometimes not be realized or may face external obstacles. The power of common sense is that it looks for ways to overcome these obstacles, takes creative initiative and creates a new healthy environment. Introverted desires should not be considered as the opposite of social activity. Their role in creating a model of behavior and healthy lifestyle cannot be forgotten. Creativity is the activation and actualization of internal mental factors requires. In order for a person to realize that he is a conscious subject capable of creating something, he must actualize and activate his inner creative forces. President Sh.M. Mirziyoev emphasized this: "Today, in order to renew and modernize our country, to develop it on an innovative basis, to implement the multifaceted and complex tasks that we have set before ourselves, we are modern and creative thinkers and take responsibility in any situation. "We are entrusting important tasks in the management of the state and society to capable, enthusiastic, high intellectual potential, patriotic young personnel." In these words introverted and extroverted forms of creativity are harmoniously mentioned. He encourages young people to do bold, innovative research. Such activity and creativity are events that are consistent with a healthy society and common sense. If a society is limited to its past and created traditions, does not go beyond showing off and praising its ethno-cultural achievements, such a society will freeze in one place and lag behind the progress of humanity. A healthy thinking society and its members critically analyze their actions and achievements, find modern ways to move forward, create new models and boldly introduce them to social existence. A society with such power is undoubtedly a healthy society. Creativity is honored by the fact that it is directed to change and improve the external existence, people's lives. Extraversion gives them sociability, usefulness to people, orientation to development.

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